

TRAJECTORY GENERATION AND PID-BASED CONTROL OF A FOUR MECANUM-WHEELED MOBILE ROBOT IN A ROS-GAZEBO SIMULATION FRAMEWORK

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17211760>

Abstract. *This study presents the modeling, trajectory generation, and control of a four mecanum-wheeled mobile robot using the Robot Operating System (ROS) integrated with the Gazebo simulation environment. Leveraging both kinematic and dynamic models, cubic polynomial trajectory generation was applied to plan robot motion, while a Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) controller was employed to ensure accurate tracking. The robot's kinematic parameters were defined through Unified Robot Description Format (URDF) modeling, and velocity commands were transmitted to each wheel while feedback was obtained from odometry data. Simulation experiments were conducted for linear and diagonal trajectories, and the influence of PID parameters on position and velocity errors was analyzed. Results demonstrate that carefully tuned PID gains significantly reduce tracking error, ensuring smooth and stable motion along the desired path. The proposed framework highlights the potential of combining ROS and Gazebo as a cost-effective and flexible platform for developing, testing, and refining control strategies prior to real-world implementation.*

Keywords: *mecanum wheeled mobile robot, Trajectory generation, Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) control, Robot operating system (ROS), Gazebo.*

Introduction

Mobile robots are equipped with the ability to move automatically and possess the capability to learn and make decisions based on sensor information. In a dynamic environment, mobile robots are expected to determine movement paths akin to humans, with performance criteria including integrity, rapid response, shorter travel distances, and reduced time consumption (Yan & Li, 2016). In today's technology, mecanum wheels are preferred for mobile robots due to the diversity in their mobility in many areas (Keek et al., 2019). Mecanum wheels contain more than one role so that they can move by creating force between the surface and the wheel. Additionally, since they have a certain angle, their movement variations are quite high. Due to these features, mobile robots with mechanical wheels can move in different directions without changing their orientation. At the same time, it can be operated with one or two wheel movements without applying torque to all wheels for a direction and speed. Mecanum wheels theoretically increase the degree of freedom of the vehicle in which they are used. It was first invented in 1970 by Bengt ILON, one of the engineers of the Swedish company Mecanum AB (Han et al., 2010).

When reviewing the literature, it becomes clear that trajectory generation for mecanum-wheeled mobile robots has emerged as a significant research focus, particularly in industrial applications where it has provided solutions to a variety of challenges. For instance, Chen et al. (2022) demonstrated that an adaptive motion tracking control method, based on characteristic modeling, enabled angular velocity control without overshoot while maintaining accurate

trajectory tracking when compared with traditional PID controllers. Similarly, Alakshendra and Chiddarwar (2017) showed through simulations and experiments that the ARSSMC controller not only exhibited excellent tracking performance but also required less control energy and provided smoother control inputs than both ARSMC and PID approaches. Their findings, grounded in Lyapunov stability theory, confirmed the asymptotic stability of the proposed control law. In another study, Hasana and Alwan (2021) evaluated a BSC-T1FLC-PSO controller and reported that it was capable of following arbitrary trajectories with high precision, as evidenced by the close alignment between desired and actual robot paths. Kim (2020) introduced innovative trajectory design strategies using straight lines and fifth-degree Bézier curves to simplify the computational process for optimal path planning. However, assumptions such as constant pseudo-velocity along curves resulted in occasional torque saturation and slightly slower performance than real-time optimal trajectories. Addressing another practical challenge, Xie et al. (2020) proposed representing robot trajectories with polynomial functions tailored to energy consumption profiles, demonstrating a promising solution to improve energy efficiency in industrial mecatronics-wheeled robots.

In this study, the trajectories are obtained using cubic polynomials method for a four mecatronics-wheeled mobile robot were utilized, and the robot was controlled using PID control method in Gazebo simulation environment with ROS. ROS, short for Robot Operating System, serves as an open-source platform for robot software, offering functionalities akin to those of a conventional operating system. These include hardware abstraction, device management, inter-process communication, and file handling. Additionally, ROS provides a suite of tools and libraries facilitating code development, debugging, and execution across diverse workstations. Complementing ROS, Gazebo stands as a 3D simulator, furnishing robots, sensors, and environment models essential for realistic 3D simulations crucial in robot development. Powered by a robust physics engine, Gazebo delivers immersive simulations tailored to the needs of developers (Koenig & Howard, 2004).

Simulation Setup

In this study, the "zm robot" model in Figure 1, a mobile robot with four mecatronics wheels, previously built using ROS, was used. The wheels of this model are 45-degree mecatronics wheels. The necessary gazebo simulations were made using this model. The trajectory equations for the movement of the mobile robot required in the simulations were sent to the robot using "cmd vel" commands, and the data from the "odom" subject was also processed in the error calculations. Thus, the necessary error calculation for the PID controller was made and added to the speed of the robot.

Robot Operating System(ROS). The Robot Operating System (ROS) is a widely adopted open-source framework that provides a unified platform for developing robotic applications. It offers a rich collection of libraries, packages, and integration tools designed to support a broad range of robotic tasks. A typical ROS package contains both functional and auxiliary files that enable specific operations while ensuring compatibility with other packages. At its core, ROS organizes software into modular units called nodes, allowing developers to design systems as small, independent, and concurrent processes. Communication between these nodes is handled through topics, where a node can publish messages for others to subscribe to, thereby facilitating seamless information exchange (Basavanna & Shivakumar, 2020). In this study, ROS forms the backbone of the system, handling inter-node communication, transmitting control commands to the robot, and processing feedback data from onboard sensors and odometry.

Figure 1. Mobile robot model in Gazebo

Gazebo Simulation Environment. Gazebo is a powerful 3D multi-robot simulator that provides realistic virtual environments for testing and validating robotic systems. It combines the OpenGL-based graphics rendering engine OGRE with the dynamic engine ODE to simulate rigid-body interactions. These bodies possess physical properties such as inertia, velocity, friction, and mass, enabling simulated robots to respond authentically to forces like pushing, pulling, or collisions. Gazebo also supports flexible visualization, allowing researchers to observe robot behavior from different camera perspectives (Du et al., 2014). In this study, Gazebo was employed to construct the simulation environment, offering a safe and cost-effective platform for trajectory and control experiments prior to real-world implementation.

Kinematic Model. Robot kinematics is a field of robotics that deals with the position and movements of robots. Kinematic analyzes have a very important place in determining how any joint of the robot will move to the desired position at the desired speed, in which direction and speed the wheels will move for mobile robots, or what angles the joints should take for robot arms. Thanks to kinematic analysis, understanding the movement of robots has become much easier. Additionally, kinematic analyzes can be divided into two groups. Forward and inverse kinematics. Forward kinematics is used to specify the robot's position and motion. The position and speed of the tip of the robot arms are found with this method. Inverse kinematics helps find the speed, direction and angle values that the joints of the robot must take to move to a certain position. Thanks to kinematic analysis, path planning can be made for mobile robots, which is one of the aims of this article.

Robot kinematics is important for industrial robots, surgical robots, service robots, and many other types of robots. This space is used to ensure that robots move correctly, perform their tasks effectively, and operate safely.

Mecanum Wheels. Mecanum wheel refers to a wheel with a special design that can move in many directions. These wheels are generally preferred for four-wheeled vehicles for their maneuverability and variety of movements. Thanks to this wheel, the robot can easily perform many types of movements such as sideways, diagonal, forward and backward. Mobile robots with mecanum wheels can easily move no matter how narrow the working environment is, thanks to this variety of movements. Mecanum wheel has such advantages as well as disadvantages. For example, the complex structure of the wheel can make its production difficult and increase its cost. Additionally, in some applications, the maximum load carrying and speed it can reach may be lower compared to other wheels.

Mecanum wheels are often used in industrial applications, material handling systems and special purpose robots. They are especially preferred in applications that require movement in

narrow spaces and fast maneuvering. However, the most suitable wheel for the job may vary depending on the requirements of the job. The following information can be given about the mecanum wheel from the literature:

In 1973, Bengt Ilon, an engineer at the Swedish company Mecanum A.B., introduced the Mecanum wheel (often referred to as the Ilon wheel). This innovative design incorporates passive rollers mounted at a 45° angle to the wheel plane, enabling omnidirectional motion with relatively low torque requirements. By redirecting a portion of the rotational force laterally through the angled rollers, the wheel allows in-place rotation and smooth maneuverability across multiple directions. Mecanum wheels have since been widely adopted in applications such as wheelchairs, forklifts, and mobile robots, where agile and flexible movement is essential. Their ability to provide holonomic motion without changing the robot's orientation makes them particularly valuable in constrained or dynamic environments (Lin et al., 2013).

As a mecanum wheel rotates, one or two rollers are typically in contact with the ground at any given time. Since only a small portion of each cylindrical roller touches the surface, the contact area shifts laterally depending on the wheel's rotation. This interaction generates a traction force in the transverse direction of the roller's contact surface. From a top view, the resulting traction force is observed to be perpendicular to the axis of the wheel. A Swedish-type omnidirectional wheel, such as the mecanum, exhibits three degrees of freedom: wheel rotation, roller rotation, and rotational slip about the vertical axis passing through the contact point (Figure 2). The velocity of the wheel can be decomposed into two components: an active component aligned with the roller axis, and a passive component perpendicular to it. Together, these forces produce both longitudinal and lateral motion. By independently controlling each wheel, the overall movement vector of the vehicle can be altered instantaneously, allowing smooth and agile omnidirectional motion (Adascalitei & Doroftei, 2011).

Figure 2. DOF's in a mecanum wheel (Adascalitei & Doroftei, 2011)

Additionally, the diverse motion capabilities of a four-wheeled mecanum robot can be illustrated through simple examples. When all four wheels rotate forward at the same speed, the robot advances in a straight line. Conversely, if the second and fourth wheels remain stationary while the first and third wheels move forward, the robot follows a diagonal path. Such combinations of wheel rotations enable a wide variety of translational and rotational movements without requiring the robot to change its orientation. Figure 2 illustrates these possible motion variations for a four-wheeled mecanum platform.

Mobile Robot Kinematics

Robot kinematics concerns the configuration of robots within a workspace, their geometric parameters, and the constraints that shape their trajectories. The formulation of kinematic equations is closely tied to the structural design of the robot. For instance, stationary manipulators

may exhibit Cartesian, cylindrical, or spherical configurations, whereas mobile robots typically employ one or more wheels that may operate with or without motion constraints. Kinematics provides the essential foundation for analyzing robot dynamics, ensuring stability, and developing effective control strategies. Its continued development remains a vital area of research in robotics. In the case of mecaum-wheeled robots, the rollers mounted at an angle transform part of the wheel's rotational force into a lateral component. As a result, the combined contributions of each wheel generate a resultant force vector in any desired direction. This enables the robot to achieve omnidirectional mobility, moving freely along the resultant vector without the need to reorient its wheels (Doroftei et al., 2007).

Forward Kinematics. Forward Kinematic Analysis is of great importance in the field of robotics as a fundamental tool for motion planning and control integration. Forward Kinematic Analysis facilitates insight into the intricate relationship between wheel speeds and the overall motion of the robot, allowing the development of precise control algorithms, trajectory optimization strategies, and reliable localization techniques. This analysis plays an important role for dynamic analysis and helps identify and mitigate stability problems. Additionally, Forward Kinematic Analysis supports efficient simulation and prototyping, allowing engineers to refine their designs before physical implementation. In essence, a comprehensive understanding of Forward Kinematic Analysis is essential to exploit the full potential of Mecanum Wheeled robots in a variety of applications, from autonomous navigation to industrial automation.

Inverse Kinematics. Inverse Kinematic Analysis is an essential for the optimization and control of the four Mecanum wheeled mobile robot, serving as an important link between high-level control commands and the wheel speeds required to achieve the desired movements.

Figure 3. Robot motion according to the direction and angular speed of the wheels (Lin et al., 2013)

The importance of Inverse Kinematic Analysis lies in its contribution to precise control, allowing complex maneuvers, accurate positioning and effective navigation in various environments. This analysis is essential for applications that require human-robot interaction, as it facilitates the translation of user-specified movements into the robot's movement. Additionally, Inverse Kinematic Analysis supports real-time adaptability, allowing the robot to respond dynamically to changing conditions. Its role in simulation and optimization enables the refinement of control strategies prior to physical implementation and reinforces their importance in realizing the full potential of Mecanum wheeled robots in a range of practical applications. The movement vector of the mobile robot is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 4. Movement vector and coordinate system of mobile robot platform (Mohand et al., 2022)

The inverse kinematic model of the robot is formulated from the motion vector of the four-wheeled mobile platform. The robot's velocity vector, denoted as v , can be decomposed into its components v_x and v_y which are aligned with the x- and y-axes of the coordinate system, respectively. These components are expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} v_x &= v \cos(\theta) \\ v_y &= v \sin(\theta) \end{aligned}$$

where v_x and v_y represent the translational velocities along the Cartesian axes. The roller angle each wheels of $\gamma_i: \{\pi/4, -\pi/4, -\pi/4, \pi/4\}$. The velocity vector equation of the mobile robot toward coordinate system component can be calculated by

$$\begin{aligned} v_i + rv_i \cos(\gamma_i) &= v_x - b_i \\ rv_i \sin(\gamma_i) &= v_y + a_i \\ v_i &= v_x - b_i \omega - \frac{v_y + a_i \omega}{\tan(\gamma_i)} \end{aligned}$$

Since $\tan(\gamma_i)$ are denoted in (5) by $\tan(\gamma_i): \{1, -1, -1, 1\}$, the linear velocity of the wheels are

$$\begin{aligned} v_1 &= v_x - v_y - a\omega - b \\ v_2 &= v_x + v_y + a\omega + b \\ v_3 &= v_x + v_y - a\omega - b \\ v_4 &= v_x - v_y + a\omega + b \end{aligned}$$

While the angular velocities of the wheels are defined as $v_i = \omega_i R$ and R is the radius of four wheels.

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{bmatrix} \omega_1 \\ \omega_2 \\ \omega_3 \\ \omega_4 \end{bmatrix} &= \frac{1}{R} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & -(a+b) \\ 1 & 1 & (a+b) \\ 1 & 1 & -(a+b) \\ 1 & -1 & (a+b) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} V_x \\ V_y \\ \omega \end{bmatrix} \\ \begin{bmatrix} V_x \\ V_y \\ \omega \end{bmatrix} &= \frac{1}{R} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ -1 & 1 & 1 & -1 \\ -(a+b) & (a+b) & -(a+b) & (a+b) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \omega_1 \\ \omega_2 \\ \omega_3 \\ \omega_4 \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

These equations present the inverse kinematic formulation used to compute the angular velocity of each wheel based on the input velocities v_x , v_y and ω . This relationship incorporates the lateral direction angle θ , enabling the robot to achieve the desired motion without altering its overall orientation (Keek et al., 2019).

Dynamic Model of Mecanum Wheeled Mobile Robots

Robot dynamics is the field of robotics that examines how the robot's components interact with the environment during its movement. Robot dynamics have become more understandable thanks to dynamic analysis. Dynamic analysis is used to better understand issues such as force, torque, velocity and acceleration between the robot's joints. Robot dynamics is important for industrial robots, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), surgical robots, and other automated systems. This area enables robots to move precisely and effectively, facilitates safe interaction with their environment, and enables robots to perform specific tasks. The Mecanum Wheeled Mobile Robot, which moves on a planar surface, was developed using the Lagrange method. Using the Lagrange method the dynamics is obtained as:

$$M\theta'' + D\theta' = T$$

M is the system parameter associated with the robot itself and is a four-dimensional invertible matrix, and lagrange dynamics equation can be rewritten as

$$\theta''(t) + M^{-1}D\theta'(t) = M^{-1}T(t)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} A + B + J_\omega & -B & B & A - B \\ -B & A + B + J_\omega & A - B & B \\ B & A - B & A + B + J_\omega & -B \\ A - B & B & -B & A + B + J_\omega \end{bmatrix}$$

$$A = \frac{mR^2}{8}$$

$$B = \frac{J_z R^2}{16(L + W)^2}$$

Where $\theta = [\theta_1 \ \theta_2 \ \theta_3 \ \theta_4]^T$, $T = [T_1 \ T_2 \ T_3 \ T_4]^T$ denote the rotation angle and the torque of the each wheels, respectively. $D = [D_1 \ D_2 \ D_3 \ D_4]^T$ is coefficient of the wheel's viscous friction. m is the mass of the robot. J_z, J_ω denote the moment of inertia of the chassis's body and the wheels, respectively (Mohand and Mellah, 2022).

Trajectory Generation

Trajectory generation, which is one of the purposes of this article, refers to the path that a robot must follow in order to perform a certain job. With this method, the speed and position of the robot can be smoothly changed depending on time. The points that need to be considered in order to perform trajectory generation are as follows:

The first step is usually to determine the points where the robot must go to achieve a task. These points usually represent multiple points from a starting point to a goal, or they can represent two points, starting and ending points. It is also important at this stage to take into account obstacles and other restrictions in the robot's working environment

Once a path is determined, it is necessary to determine how the robot should move along this path. Trajectory involves position, velocity, and acceleration changing over time. These parameters need to be carefully designed to ensure smooth movement of the robot and comply with various dynamic constraints. During trajectory generation, the kinematic and dynamic constraints of the robot must be respected. This specifically means that factors such as speed, acceleration and torque remain within certain limits. These restrictions are important for security and performance. Trajectory generation usually involves an optimization process. This aims to find the best path drawing according to a certain criterion. By using the optimization results, the robot

can monitor its trajectories in real time. During the movement of the robot, fixed target positions and velocity flow are provided for the robot controller to follow. The determination of the robot position as a function of time is called trajectory. In some cases the orbit is completely determined by the mission. In some cases, for example, when the mission is to move from one location to another at a specific time, we can adjust the orbit to meet these constraints. This work is trajectory planning. The trajectory must be a function of time and must obey given limits on joint velocities, accelerations, or torques(Lynch & Park, 2017). For example for simulation in gazebo, firstly we assume that the robot on origin (0,0) and the robot moves on x-axis through 5 meters in 30 seconds. For this path, we can basicly use cubic polynomials method. The results of calculations is following:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{desired}_{position}: x(t) &= a_0 + a_1t + a_2t^2 + a_3t^3 \\ \text{desired}_{velocity}: x'(t) &= a_1 + 2a_2t + 3a_3t^2 \\ \text{desired}_{acceleration}: x''(t) &= 2a_2 + 3a_3t \\ x(t) &= 0.016t^2 - 0.0003t^3 \\ x'(t) &= 0.033t - 0.001t^2 \end{aligned}$$

For example we assume that the robot on origin (0,0) and the robot moves on x-axis through 3 meters and on y-axis 4 meters in 30 seconds. For this path, we can basicly use cubic polynomials method. The results of calculations is following:

In x-axis:

$$\begin{aligned} x(t) &= 0.01t^2 - 0.0002t^3 \\ x'(t) &= 0.02t - 0.0006t^2 \end{aligned}$$

In y-axis:

$$\begin{aligned} y(t) &= 0.013t^2 - 0.0003t^3 \\ y'(t) &= 0.026t - 0.0008t^2 \end{aligned}$$

For trajectory generation, the higher order polynomials method can also be used, such as the cubic polynomials method above. Trajectory examples with fifth degree polynomials can be given as follows. Firstly, the equations of position, velocity and acceleration respectively as following:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{desired}_{position}: x(t) &= a_0 + a_1t + a_2t^2 + a_3t^3 + a_4t^4 + a_5t^5 \\ \text{desired}_{velocity}: x'(t) &= a_1 + 2a_2t + 3a_3t^2 + 4a_4t^3 + 5a_5t^4 \\ \text{desired}_{acceleration}: x''(t) &= 2a_2 + 6a_3t + 12a_4t^2 + 20a_5t^3 \end{aligned}$$

The general solution for these equations is:

$$\begin{aligned} a_0 &= x(0) \\ a_1 &= x'(0) \\ a_2 &= \frac{x''(0)}{2} \\ a_3 &= \frac{20x(f) - 20x(0) - (8x'(f) + 12x'(0))t_f - (3x''(0) - x''(f))t_f^2}{2t_f^3} \\ a_4 &= \frac{30x(0) - 30x(f) + (14x'(f) + 16x'(0))t_f + (3x''(0) - 2x''(f))t_f^2}{2t_f^4} \\ a_5 &= \frac{12x(f) - 12x(0) - (6x'(f) + 6x'(0))t_f - (x''(0) - x''(f))t_f^2}{2t_f^5} \end{aligned}$$

Apart from the cubic and higher order methods given above, other trajectory equations found in the literature can also be used for this purpose. In addition, one of the main purposes of these operations should be for the robot to draw a smoother path. Talking about the different

methods, Linear Interpolation, although a simple method, provides drawing a linear path between a starting and target position. Polynomial Interpolation can be used to create more complex paths. Splines are used like polynomials, but are generally lower order and more smoothly connected. Cubic splines are especially popular. It contains polynomials designed to meet specific speed and acceleration conditions by specifying a starting and target position. Optimization Methods try to find the best path by minimizing a cost function with various mathematical methods. Using the kinematic and dynamic model of the robot, an optimal path drawing can be created for a specific application. This is usually done by solving differential equations or optimizing forward kinematic/dynamic models.

PID Control

The Proportional–Integral–Derivative (PID) controller is a widely adopted closed-loop control strategy in both industrial practice and academic research, primarily due to its straightforward implementation and reliable performance. It operates by combining three control actions: proportional, integral, and derivative. The fundamental objective of feedback control is to minimize the error signal, defined as the difference between the system’s measured output and the desired reference value. The proportional term generates a corrective action directly proportional to the instantaneous error. The integral term eliminates steady-state errors by accumulating the error over time, compensating for offsets that the proportional term alone cannot resolve. The derivative term anticipates future error behavior by responding to the rate of change of the error, thereby improving system stability and damping oscillations. Together, these three components form a balanced control law that ensures accuracy, stability, and robustness in dynamic systems (Mohand Saidi & Mellah, 2022).

$$u(t) = K_p e(t) + K_i \int_0^t e(t) dt + K_d \frac{de(t)}{dt}$$

where $u(t)$ is the control input, $e(t)$ is the instantaneous value of error, K_p, K_i, K_d are coefficients of proportional, integral and derivative terms.

Simulation Results

First Trajectory From initial point (0, 0) to final point (5, 0). The first trajectory was tested in the simulation environment, and the error graph of the robot's speed in Figure 4 was obtained, while the PID parameters were provided in Table 1. Additionally, efforts were made to reduce the error value by adjusting the PID parameters. Increasing the P value results in faster convergence to the target, whereas increasing the D value leads to increased deceleration of the robot as it approaches the target.

Table 1. PID Parameters of First Trajectory for Velocity Control

PID Parameters	Value
Proportional(P)	120.0
Integral(I)	0.0
Derivative(D)	2.0
Sampling Time(dt)	0.01

Table 2. PID Parameters of First Trajectory for Position Control

PID Parameters	Value
Proportional(P)	50.0
Integral(I)	0.0
Derivative(D)	2.0
Sampling Time(dt)	0.01

Figure 5. Error Graph of Velocity In X Direction (m/s)

Figure 6. Error Graph of Position in X Direction (m)

Second Trajectory From initial point (0, 0) to final point (3, 4). The second trajectory was tested in the simulation environment, and the error graph of the robot's velocity in the x-direction in Figure 5 and in the y-direction in Figure 6 was obtained. PID parameters for both directions are provided in Table 3. Efforts were made to reduce the error value by adjusting the PID parameters. Increasing the P value results in faster convergence to the target, whereas increasing the D value leads to increased deceleration of the robot as it approaches the target.

Table 3. PID parameters for bot X and Y directions

PID Parameters	Value for X Direction	Value for Y direction
Proportional(P)	5.0	125.0
Integral(I)	0.0	0.0
Derivative(D)	15.0	15.0
Sampling Time(dt)	0.01	0.01

Figure 7. Error graph of velocity in X direction (m/s)

Figure 8. Error graph of velocity in Y direction (m/s)

Conclusion

This research has demonstrated the effective control of a four mecanum-wheeled mobile robot through trajectory generation and PID-based feedback within the ROS–Gazebo simulation framework. By integrating kinematic analysis, trajectory equations, and real-time error correction, the robot successfully followed predefined paths with reduced error. The results confirm that PID tuning plays a critical role in balancing response speed and stability, offering an adaptable control method for omnidirectional robots. Beyond simulation, the developed methodology provides a practical foundation for real-world applications where agile and precise motion is required, such as industrial automation, service robotics, and logistics. Future work will focus on transferring the proposed control strategies to physical prototypes, incorporating advanced controllers such as

adaptive or intelligent approaches, and comparing simulation performance with experimental outcomes to further validate and optimize the system.

REFERENCES

1. Adascalitei, F., & Doroftei, I. (2011). Practical Applications for Mobile Robots based on Mecanum Wheels-a Systematic Survey. *Proceedings of International Conference On Innovations, Recent Trends And Challenges In Mechatronics, Mechanical Engineering And New High-Tech Products Development*, vol. 3.
2. Alakshendra, V., & Chiddarwar, S. S. (2017). Adaptive robust control of Mecanum-wheeled mobile robot with uncertainties. *Nonlinear Dynamics*, 87(4), 2147–2169. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11071-016-3179-1/METRICS>.
3. Basavanna, M., & Shivakumar, M. (2020). Mapping of an Unknown Indoor Environment Using 2D-Lidar and ROS for Mobile Robot Navigation. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, 14338 – 14345.
4. Chen, X., Cheng, L., & Li, T. (2022). Adaptive Motion Tracking Control for Omnidirectional Mobile Robots Based on Characteristic Model. *Chinese Control Conference*, July, 2876–2881. <https://doi.org/10.23919/CCC55666.2022.9902188>.
5. Doroftei, I., Grosu, V., & Spinu, V. (2007). Omnidirectional Mobile Robot - Design and Implementation. *Bioinspiration and Robotics Walking and Climbing Robots*, InTech Open. <https://doi.org/10.5772/5518>.
6. Du, Z., Sun, Y., Su, Y., & Dong, W. (2014). A ROS/Gazebo based method in developing virtual training scene for upper limb rehabilitation. *Proceedings of 2014 IEEE International Conference on Progress in Informatics and Computing*, 307–311. <https://doi.org/10.1109/PIC.2014.6972347>.
7. Hasana, S., & Alwan, H. (2021). Modeling and Control of Wheeled Mobile Robot With Four Mecanum Wheels. *Engineering and Technology Journal*, 39(5A), 779–789. <https://doi.org/10.30684/ETJ.V39I5A.1926>.
8. Keek, J. S., Loh, S. L., & Chong, S. H. (2019). Comprehensive Development and Control of a Path-Trackable Mecanum-Wheeled Robot. *IEEE Access*, 7, 18368–18381. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2897013>.
9. Kim, J. (2020). Trajectory generation of a two-wheeled mobile robot in an uncertain environment. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, 67(7), 5586–5594. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIE.2019.2931506>
10. K.-L. Han, H. Kim and J. S. Lee. (2010). The Sources of Position Errors of Omni-Directional Mobile Robot with Mecanum Wheel. *IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man and Cybernetics*. pp. 581-586.
11. Koenig, N., & Howard, A. (2004). Design and use paradigms for Gazebo, an open-source multi-robot simulator. *IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*. Vol. 3, 2149–2154. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IROS.2004.1389727>.
12. Lin, L.-C., Shih, H.-Y., Lin, L.-C., & Shih, H.-Y. (2013). Modeling and Adaptive Control of an Omni-Mecanum-Wheeled Robot. *Intelligent Control and Automation*, 4(2), 166–179. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ICA.2013.42021>.
13. Lynch, K. M., & Park, F. C. (2017). *Modern Robotics Mechanics, Planning, And Control*. Cambridge University Press.
14. Mohand, S., & Mellah, R. (2022). Real-Time Speed Control of a Mobile Robot Using PID Controller. *Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, 413 LNNS, 548–556. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-96311-8_51.

15. Xie, L., Stol, K., & Xu, W. (2020). Energy-Optimal Motion Trajectory of an Omni-Directional Mecanum-Wheeled Robot via Polynomial Functions. *Robotica*. 38(8), 1400–1414. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S026357471900153X>.
16. Yan, Y., & Li, Y. (2016). Mobile robot autonomous path planning based on fuzzy logic and filter smoothing in dynamic environment. *Proceedings of the World Congress on Intelligent Control and Automation (WCICA)*. September, 1479–1484. <https://doi.org/10.1109/WCICA.2016.7578767>.